

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FACTORS HINDERING THE DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Every state must adopt a well-considered political course and foster an active civil society, including non-governmental organizations and other civic unions, as these elements serve to strengthen and unify the nation. When analyzing the contemporary political situation, both in political and academic circles, the lack of a robust civil society or its weakness is frequently highlighted among the challenges faced by society and the country.

Keywords: civil society, post-socialist transformation, civil society organizations.

1. Factors Hindering the Development of Civil Society in Georgia

Since Georgia gained independence, discussions on the reasons for the failure and/or delays in the post-socialist transformation have become increasingly relevant. For more than thirty years, Georgia has been a model of unfulfilled opportunities and dashed hopes. Low development rates and a challenging social backdrop stem from the underdevelopment of democracy, which, in turn, is linked to the underdevelopment of civil society.

The formation of civil society begins with the emergence of civil organizations in their early forms. There is no universally accepted definition of a civil organization. According to EU policy documents, a civil organization is defined as "a non-governmental, non-profit structure that is impartial and non-violent, where individuals unite to achieve common goals and implement ideas, whether they are political, cultural, societal, or economic in nature." A civil organization actively collaborates with both citizens and the government, influencing policy formation and the decision-making process.

Civil society organizations play a crucial role in policymaking, influencing the formation of policy agendas, as well as ensuring their oversight and monitoring. A strong civil society fosters an inclusive and participatory process, allowing the ideas of all stakeholders to be shared and reflected in relevant policy decisions, laws, regulations, and strategies. Achieving this requires civil society organizations to possess appropriate experience, skills, internal cohesion, and public trust.

Numerous studies conducted in Georgia reveal a very low level of civic engagement among its citizens. According to a public opinion survey supported by GPAC,⁵⁸ only 1–5% of the population reports membership in a non-governmental organization or trade union, about 0.8% belongs to an official cultural or sports union, and less than 5% indicate having any form of connection with civil organizations. Furthermore, the level

of political engagement is similarly low, with only 2% of the population affiliated with a political party.

These findings underscore the limited role of civil society and its low involvement in the socio-political life of the country. This lack of engagement negatively impacts Georgia's political agenda, leading to reduced government accountability, shortcomings in democratic governance, challenges in civic education, and hindered socio-economic development.

Despite the low levels of public involvement, approximately 15,000 NGOs are registered in Georgia—a figure that has often been the subject of criticism, particularly given the country's population of 3.7 million. Nonetheless, the creation of NGOs has continued unabated. In light of the current situation, it is essential for society to focus on increasing the level of civil society activity and engagement.

In the scientific literature, civil society is often treated as a singular entity, with little emphasis on the concept of institutional⁵⁹ civil society.⁶⁰ At the same time, the term is frequently used exclusively to refer to institutional civil society. This underscores the need for the introduction and recognition of a new term in academic discourse—a qualitatively different phenomenon, distinct from both natural and institutional civil society and entirely unrelated to traditional civil societies. For countries undergoing post-socialist transformation, particularly Georgia, this phenomenon can be termed as "professional civil society," commonly referred to as "grant-guzzling."⁶¹

In traditional democracies based on civil society, a significant portion of public activity stems from volunteerism, and a notable share of project funding is derived from private donations through "fundraising" and "crowdfunding." In these systems, civil society institutions emerge as guiding forces, steering initiatives where volunteers continue to play a substantial role.

In contrast, civil society in post-socialist transformation countries—especially in Georgia—develops differently. Civil society institutions are established not as an organic expression of internal societal demand,

⁵⁸ https://crrc.ge/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/final_gpac_2014_civic_engagement_report_04.08.2014_geo.pdf

⁵⁹ <http://www.nplg.gov.ge/greenstone3/library/collection/civil2/document/HASH24605b417cf29ce3be098b.3?p.s=TextQuery>

⁶⁰ <https://www.cipdd.org/upload/files/POLICY.PDF>

⁶¹ <https://caucasusbarometer.org/ge/ks2017ge/ACTGRAN/>

but as externally initiated entities heavily reliant on grants from foreign and international funds.⁶² These organizations do not operate based on private volunteer donations but are driven by grants allocated by major foundations and staffed by contracted "professionals," either on a long-term or short-term basis. This externally driven and grant-dependent model diverges significantly from traditional volunteer-based civil societies.

In reality, what we are observing is not the presence of genuine civil society institutions but rather an imitation of them. These are entities that outwardly resemble civil society but fail to embody its core principles, as they are established on a professional rather than grassroots basis. The large number of NGOs in the country highlights the weakness of the state sector. NGOs often step in to participate in the creation or management of services that the state is unable to implement effectively.

The NGO sector assumes responsibility for addressing the needs of specific target groups, working alongside the state sector to deliver services that are crucial for society. Naturally, the proliferation of NGOs in a country signals areas where the state is falling short. From this perspective, there is hope that professional civil society may one day evolve into a genuine civil society. However, this transformation will likely occur only when the workforce within the non-governmental sector is "diluted" with volunteers.

This shift could be further supported by the growing trend of a middle class in the country, which is essential for fostering volunteerism and creating a more authentic civil society.

2. Non-Governmental Organizations

The number of NGOs in Georgia is disproportionately large,⁶³ driven by several factors, with financial interest being a primary motivator.⁶⁴ When access to funding becomes an objective, declared goals often serve as mere formalities rather than genuine missions. Additionally, the damaged image of political parties has led certain individuals to position themselves as more credible by "working" within non-governmental organizations.

Young people are often drawn to NGOs as an easy way to earn money, which subsequently fuels their ambitions. For many, politics then becomes an even simpler path to gaining status and resources with minimal effort. This dynamic has led to the emergence of a distorted form of institutional civil society in Georgia—one defined by professional civil society rather than grassroots engagement.

In a country characterized by high rates of higher education but low employment opportunities, professional civil society has become a springboard for many, serving as a stepping stone to political careers or economic advancement.

Among the key factors impeding the development of civil society in Georgia are the low level of communication between NGOs and the public, as well as the general lack of information about non-governmental organizations.⁶⁵ Experience shows that the communication strategies employed by civil society organizations with their target audiences are often limited in scope and accessibility, even on social media platforms.⁶⁶

Addressing this issue partially requires improving public relations campaigns, involving individuals with high reputation and expertise within civil society organizations, adopting innovative technologies and outreach methods to connect with broader segments of society, and fostering long-term, close cooperation with beneficiaries.

Additionally, civil society organizations often encounter various challenges when engaging with state agencies. For instance, the formats of interaction between analytical public organizations and government bodies frequently fail to achieve their intended outcomes. Even when these organizations produce high-quality, professional products, the state may avoid collaborating with them. This avoidance is often attributed to criticisms that such organizations are overly critical or politicized. As a result, the valuable contributions of these organizations are sometimes disregarded, further hampering their effectiveness.

It is also common for the government, due to the low visibility of the NGO sector in the political sphere, to disregard it as a creator of the public agenda and perceive it as incapable of contributing meaningfully to the policymaking process. In its communication with the sector, the government often emphasizes that NGOs rely solely on donor funding, casting doubt on the sector's effectiveness and leaving its initiatives and recommendations largely ignored.

Experience shows⁶⁷ that the communication strategies of analytical organizations are often unappealing to state agencies. Similarly, organizations engaged in monitoring and human rights protection face significant difficulties in obtaining timely or complete information from state structures. Delays in the information retrieval process are almost routine, and it is not uncommon for the responses provided by state agencies to be incomplete.⁶⁸

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<https://csogeorgia.org/storage/app/uploads/public/60c1e9/2d/60c1e9e2d0685306575183.pdf>

⁶³ <https://csogeorgia.org/ge/post/viskonsinis-shtatis-gamotsdileba>

⁶⁴ <https://eu4georgia.eu/the-world-ngo-day/#:~:text=There%20are%20nearly%2010%20000,%2C%20prevention%2C%20promotion%20and%20transformation>

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<https://csogeorgia.org/storage/app/uploads/public/5cd/dc3/2d3/5cddc32d33877279473948.pdf>

⁶⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/project-result-content/302cfb1-1f33-4067-ade5-a21b5d5b02e4/Challenges_and_pathways_for_promoting_Democratic_Principles_and_Civic_Education_in_Georgia.pdf

⁶⁷ <https://www.ctc.org.ge/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Civil-Society-Report-2012.pdf>

⁶⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/project-result-content/302cfb1-1f33-4067-ade5-a21b5d5b02e4/Challenges_and_pathways_for_promoting_Democratic_Principles_and_Civic_Education_in_Georgia.pdf

To enhance the effectiveness of non-governmental organizations, it is crucial to raise professional standards and diversify communication channels with state authorities. By addressing these challenges, NGOs can better position themselves as credible and impactful contributors to the public agenda and the policymaking process.

Service provider organizations encounter various difficulties in their interactions with the state. These organizations, which deliver essential services such as medication distribution,⁶⁹ juvenile justice programs, and psychological assistance, play a critical role in addressing human needs. However, according to representatives of organizations receiving state grants, the funding provided is often insufficient to deliver high-quality services.

Moreover, service provider organizations frequently take on dual roles, simultaneously serving as both service providers and monitoring or human rights organizations. This duality creates additional challenges, as the demands of monitoring and advocacy can conflict with their primary service delivery functions.

The relationship between public organizations and donors also presents notable issues.⁷⁰ Often, these relationships lack a genuine sense of partnership, despite both parties sharing the same goal: maximizing social benefits for the community and beneficiaries in the country where the donor operates. In some segments of society, there is a prevailing perception that these relationships are one-sided and unbalanced, with the imbalance stemming from the unequal power dynamics between donors and public organizations. This disparity can hinder effective collaboration and the achievement of shared objectives.

The vast majority of civil society organizations (CSOs) in Georgia rely heavily on international funding,⁷¹ with more than 95%⁷² of their funding coming from international donors. Consequently, only a small number of organizations are organizationally sustainable and able to remain focused on their mission and maintain their independence in relationships with donors, even amid shifting circumstances.

In recent years, state funding has emerged as an alternative source of support, but not all CSOs are willing to accept funding from the state. Many organizations are concerned that state funding may compromise their independence or affect their ability to operate freely.

Additionally, international donors contribute minimally to fostering philanthropy at the local level and show limited interest in supporting CSO-led fundraising campaigns. This lack of support hinders CSOs in finding alternative funding sources and developing sus-

tainable operations. Donors often provide limited encouragement for CSOs to generate additional income through entrepreneurial activities, even within funded programs. In the rare cases when donors support entrepreneurial initiatives, they seldom permit partner organizations to sell the products they create, further constraining the financial sustainability and growth of these organizations.

One of the concerns frequently expressed by civil society institutions about donors is the overly strict financial and administrative controls imposed on grantee organizations. However, the civil sector also acknowledges that the existing accountability requirements have contributed to their organizational development. These controls help improve management skills and foster the establishment of more efficient and sustainable internal management systems.

Looking ahead, public organizations must focus on diversifying their funding sources to ensure greater financial stability. For the Georgian non-governmental sector, it will be essential to collaborate with both the state and foreign donors, particularly in areas such as service provision, fostering local philanthropy, and supporting CSO-led fundraising campaigns. Strengthening these efforts will enhance the sector's ability to operate sustainably and effectively meet societal needs.

Conclusion

Civil society has undergone a long and challenging process of formation and development. From the era of ancient Greek democracy to the fall of Rome, it experienced its first significant rise, particularly in Athens and Rome between the 6th and 1st centuries BC. However, following the period of civil wars in the 1st century BC, it began to decline under the dominance of permanent military dictatorships. Later, during the Renaissance, Reformation, and Enlightenment, civil society reemerged in Western Europe, where its development has continued to evolve to this day, with its scope steadily expanding.

In Georgia, the roots and signs of civil society appeared sporadically throughout history. However, due to well-known objective reasons, meaningful development of civil society was not possible until the collapse of the Soviet Union. Currently undergoing a protracted post-socialist transformation, Georgia increasingly recognizes the critical role of civil society in fostering democratic development.

Since gaining independence, Georgia has faced numerous political crises. Every government change has effectively amounted to a regime change, often characterized by revolutionary shifts on multiple levels. Consequently, Georgia has lacked the extended periods

⁶⁹ <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/2410/2014/03/Georgian.pdf>

⁷⁰ <https://www.ctc.org.ge/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Civil-Society-Report-2012.pdf>

⁷¹ https://www.csrddg.ge/storage/files/doc/%E1%83%90%E1%83%A0%E1%83%90%E1%83%A1%E1%83%90%E1%83%AE%E1%83%94%E1%83%9A%E1%83%9B%E1%83%AC%E1%83%98%E1%83%A4%E1%83%9D_%E1%83%93%E1%83%90%E1%83%A4%E1%83%98%E1%83%9

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⁷² <https://www.ctc.org.ge/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Civil-Society-Report-2012.pdf>

of peace essential for the organic formation of civil society. Nonetheless, these political crises have acted as catalysts, prompting the gradual formation of civil society in response to these challenges.

In reality, the Georgian public, which has repeatedly anticipated rapid reforms and swift economic growth from successive governments, has consistently faced disappointment. This recurring dissatisfaction stems from the inability of any government to fully meet the population's needs and expectations, further underscoring the necessity for a robust and independent civil society.

As a result of repeated disappointments, the Georgian public's messianic expectations toward the government have diminished, and there has recently been a growing readiness among people to take initiative and address issues themselves.

Since the collapse of the Soviet Union, it has been evident that a developed civil society is essential for the establishment and advancement of democracy. Advocates of post-socialist transformation have shown significant concern for fostering civil society in Georgia. However, the irony lies in the fact that this excessive focus and "care" inadvertently led to the opposite outcome. Instead of fostering genuine civil society, a distorted version—termed "professional civil society"—emerged.

As previously mentioned, this professional civil society meets the formal criteria of civil society but qualitatively represents the opposite essence. A combination of economic hardships, high unemployment rates, political instability, and the authoritarian tendencies of the authorities (notably during the National Movement's rule), along with the professionalization of civil society, has collectively hindered the development of a true, grassroots civil society in Georgia.

Political instability, unemployment, low economic development, and high income inequality have rendered Georgia's middle class small, weak, and vulnerable.⁷³ The middle class represents the critical mass needed to "unload" the burden of a politicized and professionalized civil society. Compounding these challenges, the destructive legacy of Soviet-era vices and parasitism—warned against by Merab Mamardashvili—continues to exert influence.

Mamardashvili identified Georgia's cultural peculiarities as a primary obstacle to democratization. He emphasized that without transitioning from an ideological culture to a democratic one, Georgia's democratization process would remain delayed, contradictory, and opaque. His insights find resonance in Francis Fukuyama's discussion of "cultural wars,"⁷⁴ which outlines four stages in the consolidation of democracy. Mamardashvili's concept of replacing ideological culture with democratic culture aligns with Fukuyama's fourth stage, the cultural consolidation of democracy.

Synthesizing the perspectives of Mamardashvili and Fukuyama, one can conclude that Georgia is now at a pivotal moment, ready to cultivate a truly civilized

civic nation. This transformation will occur at Fukuyama's most complex and profound level—culture—and must be driven by a robust civil society. Civil society serves as the vital link between democratic institutions and citizens, enabling the cultural foundation necessary for sustainable democratization.

The development of the civil sector in Georgia under current conditions depends primarily on the civil society organizations (CSOs) themselves, followed by the government of Georgia and Georgian society as a whole.

The cautious stance of the current government, combined with the inflexibility and lack of functionality within some parts of the civil sector, creates a unique opportunity. This environment fosters the potential for the emergence of a non-politicized, internally donation-dependent, and sustainable civil society. Such a civil society would be oriented toward addressing the genuine needs and demands of the Georgian public.

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